

Pop-Machina

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 821479.

D8.3

Innovation, exploitation and sustainability plan (1st version)

May 2020

<http://www.popmachina.eu>

Abstract

The present document illustrates the **Innovation, exploitation and sustainability plan** of the Pop-Machina project. This deliverable at hand is part of Task 8.4 Innovation, Exploitation and Replication. The objective of this task is to ensure the exploitation and sustainability of Pop-Machina's results beyond the end of the project as well as their adoption and replication by other cities. The plan includes the Innovation and IPR Management Strategy of the project, an analysis of the market(s) that are relevant to Pop-Machina, and the project assets per individual partner. This plan will be periodically updated during the course of Pop-Machina to reflect the most recent developments of the project.

This report constitutes Deliverable 8.3, for Work Package 8 of the Pop-Machina project.

May 2020

© 2020, Pop-Machina, Collaborative production for the circular economy; a community approach, – project number 821479.

General contact: pop-machina@kuleuven.be
p.a. Pop-Machina
HIVA - Research Institute for Work and Society
Parkstraat 47 box 5300, 3000 LEUVEN, Belgium

For more information mcs@etam.gr
Schiza M., 2020, D8.3 Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (1st Version). Leuven: Pop-Machina project 821479 – H2020.

Information may be quoted provided the source is stated accurately and clearly.
This publication is also available via <http://www.pop-machina.eu>

This publication is part of the Pop-Machina project, this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 821479.

The information and views set out in this paper are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

VERSION CONTROL SHEET

Deliverable number + title	D8.3 Innovation, exploitation and sustainability plan (1st version)
Prepared by	Maroulla Schiza 3 – <i>ETAM SA</i> mcs@etam.gr
Work package number	WP8
Work package leader	White Research
Dissemination level (PU, CO)	Public
Delivery date	3/06/2020
Submission date to EC	4/06/2020
Main authors	Maroulla Schiza
Reviewers	Angela Dimitriou, Siegfried Dewitte

REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Summary of changes	Initials	Changes marked
1	18/05/2020	Draft report	MS	
2	02/06/2020	Final draft adopting feedback from reviewers	MS	

Contents

1.	Introduction	5
2.	Intellectual property rights strategy	6
2.1	Intellectual property	6
2.2	Intellectual property strategy	7
2.3	Institutional differences in IP strategy	8
2.4	IP legal environment	9
2.5	IP management	11
3.	Innovation management strategy	12
3.1	Innovation management	12
3.2	Innovation strategy	13
3.3	Innovation potential	14
4.	Markets relevant to Pop-Machina	16
4.1	The maker movement	18
4.2	Distributed production and collaborative technologies	19
5.	Project assets	21
6.	Preliminary strategies for exploitation and sustainability	24
6.1	Exploitation	24
6.1.1	Identification of the project assets	24
6.1.2	Finalisation of project assets and IP management and rights	33
6.1.3	Decide upon exploitable assets and particular rights	33
6.2	Sustainability	34
6.3	Scheduling exploitation and sustainability strategy actions	36
7.	KPIs	37
8.	Conclusions	44
9.	References	45

1. Introduction

The present document illustrates the *innovation, exploitation and sustainability plan* of the Pop-Machina project. This deliverable at hand is part of Task 8.4 Innovation, Exploitation and Replication. It is a comprehensive description of the relevant activities planned to ensure the exploitation and sustainability of Pop-Machina's results beyond the end of the project focusing on the preliminary strategies to be followed and the identification of key assets for exploitation. With this document at hand and the project management tools developed in WP1 all related *key performance indicators (KPIs)* that have been set in the project proposal alongside with the communication and dissemination plan will be addressed. It is the *first deliverable of Task 8.4* and the first version of the 'Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan'. The plan will be periodically updated during the course of Pop-Machina to reflect the most recent developments of the project (M24, M48).

The strategic target of all exploitation activities of Pop-Machina is to pave the way towards the widespread adoption and sustainability of its results beyond the end of the project, thus maximising their impact. This constitutes a major priority and challenge for our consortium, given the high potential that the project's results hold for bringing the EU into the forefront of circular regeneration.

Chapters 2 and 3 respectively give an overview of the Intellectual Property Rights and Innovation Management Strategy. The Markets relevant to Pop-Machina are presented on Chapter 4 including details on circular economy, maker spaces, distributed production and collaborative technologies. Project Assets as identified per partner at this stage of the project are presented in Chapter 5, whilst the Preliminary Strategies for exploitation and sustainability of the project and its results are presented in Chapter 6. The deliverable concludes with the relevant KPIs and a specific analysis on the degree they are satisfied by it as well as the conditions for reaching the specific targeted values.

2. Intellectual property rights strategy

Intellectual Property (IP) strategy may be interpreted in many ways. For better understanding of the significance and implications of the term, an effective comprehension of the terms *intellectual property* and *strategy* needs to be established, so as to understand how they are interconnected and how organisations are affected by an IP strategy.¹

2.1 Intellectual property

IP may be defined as a property category including intangible creations of the human intellect.² It needs to be noted that Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) are business assets and as such they should be seen as a power tool for economic growth instead of an obscure legal concept. The most common types of IP³ may be categorised⁴ as follows:

Figure 1. Common IPRs

Trademarks	Patents	Design
Signals the origin of products to consumers	Rights granted for inventions, that are either products or a processes offering new technical solutions	Protects the external appearance of the product
Utility mode	Copyrights	Trade secrets
Rights for technical inventions for a shorter period than patents	Are relative to artwork and audiovisual creations (i.e. books, music, paintings) as well as scientific works	Valuable information not to be publicly disclosed

1 <http://www.iphandbook.org/handbook/ch05/p01/>

2 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intellectual_property

3 <http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/>

4 <https://www.wipo.int/>

The above mentioned IPRs are the core ones that are expected to be encountered within the Pop-Machina project and may be of interest for most of the consortium partners; cities, academic, technical and consultants. The following figure presents them grouped as per registration needs. The registration process requires filling out the IPR application form and a statement explaining its unique characteristics.

Figure 2. IP registration needs

It is commonly considered that IP rights are simply the means to protect innovation for the innovator's benefit. This view only emphasises the innovators' private benefits disregarding the significant public benefits an IP system provides. An IP rights system when viewed broadly, has numerous components that overall support a system's effectiveness. A balance needs to be kept between public and private interests, so that the latter does not dominate the public interest. Public interests should respectively, govern the long-term private interests that drive the IP rights system.

2.2 Intellectual property strategy⁵

An organisation's IP strategy may be defined as a strategy for increasing its added value by establishing, protecting, and using intellectual property whilst considering its management resources and external environment. IPs are a key factor for building a strategy that aims for the organisations development and not the mere acquisition of IPR for research results.

Following IP rights identification and their integration into strategic management, the IP strategy requirements for making the best use of them as resources need to be explored.

A simple categorisation of IP strategy is to follow the strategic management categorisation that is distinguished into *internal and external* resources. This categorisation includes on the one hand, external to the organisation activities involving second and third-party interactions. Internal activities, on the other hand, concern management issues within organisations.

⁵ <http://www.iphandbook.org/handbook/ch05/p01/>

The main elements of *an external IP strategy* include exploitation issues as well as litigation, licensing, and learning issues. IP rights owners may prevent, permit, or even encourage the use of intellectual rights, depending on the type of the relative IP rights and their strength. What needs to be decided upon the IP rights is whether the mere ability to prevent exploitation by others will be too restrictive an attitude that may act to an organisation's disadvantage. This could mean that the owner may miss out on opportunities that diffusing technology offers to learning opportunities.

Apart from external issues an IP strategy involves a number of *internal issues* that are related to an organisation's resources. Amongst the issues that are especially relevant to IP strategy are: valuation, information, coordination, and education.

Valuation

Generally, the valuation of intellectual property signifies the IP system type (e.g. patents, industrial designs, trademarks). Eventhough the decision to acquire or maintain intellectual rights suggests they have a specific value there are many cases where it is not clear what their actual value is.

Information

The diffusion of information is amongst the IP rights roles. For example, when searching for patents, an organisation can easily perceive the technological trajectory of other organisations. This is strategically important to cope with competitors or negotiate licenses or other deals. Thus, a valuable resource is the access to any information that is likely to inform decision making.

Coordination

Coordination of the intellectual property management team is crucial, and at the same time essential to the process of strategically 'allocating resources'. Good communication and coordination of the team members that as a group possess prerequisite skills is essential for the effective IP rights management.

Education

Finally, a minimum level of IP awareness training must be achieved amongst those involved within a project. Awareness training is essential to prevent accidental compromising of vital intellectual property due to lack of education. An example would be to make a publication before filing a patent application which would invalidate the patent application.

For an accurate distinction between the concepts of *IP strategy* and *IP management*, one needs to differentiate general principles and aims that govern courses of action (strategy) from actual implementation of courses of action (management).

2.3 Institutional differences in IP strategy

IP issues need to be addressed by all types of organisation i.e., public sector organisations, spin-out companies, small-medium enterprises (SMEs), and large companies. IP issues that will need to be addressed will nonetheless be different in each case and dependent on the IP strategies they will follow.

A private company seems to be more relevant to the innovation-promoting concept of IP rights as it is expected to be seeking a commercial return, rather than an organisation of the public sector engaged in R&D for the purposes of developing government policies. Nonetheless public organisations are highly relevant to the characteristics of an IP strategy that relate to the control and intellectual resource management especially those public organisations that are expected to perform the best possible management of their resources to fulfill public objectives. Some examples of organisations of the public sector that are expected to develop an IP strategy as they are highly involved in the creation of intellectual property are health services, public research departments, university research

laboratories and other institutions. These public institutions need to make sure that their personnel can identify the main IP assets, as well as that they are properly educated on the management and preservation of all assets within the organisation. Additionally, an IP strategy can protect an organisation from liabilities such as unintentional disclosure to third parties.⁶

Therefore, an efficient and effectively enforced intellectual property framework is necessary to ensure the stimulation of investment in innovation and to avoid commercial-scale intellectual property rights (IPR) infringements that result in economic harm. The European Commission's aim is to ensure that this framework allows creators and inventors in the EU to reap appropriate returns from welfare-enhancing innovation for EU citizens.

Legal instruments, such as the Directive on enforcement already exist in the EU to prevent the infringement of intellectual property rights. This is the Directive on the enforcement of intellectual property rights,⁷ such as copyright and related rights, trademarks, designs or patents that was adopted in April 2004. The Directive requires all EU countries to apply effective, dissuasive, and proportionate remedies and penalties against those engaged in counterfeiting and piracy and aims to create a level playing field for right holders in the EU. It means that all EU countries will have a similar set of measures available for right holders to defend their intellectual property rights.

2.4 IP legal environment

The exploitation of research results is dependent on the appropriate management of IP, as an integral part of the project's knowledge management. In order for R&D results to be exploitable they generally demand additional and often significant investments. To this end it is important that they are safeguarded with intellectual property rules. Intellectual property can thus be an asset itself given that it can ensure a competitive advantage for its owners in the R&D society in the market. The protection of intellectual property rights might be a time-consuming process that requires effort and resources, nonetheless offering important advantages to research organisations and companies. It can thus enable technology transfer, and at the same time increase the possibilities for a company to grow.⁸

Pop-Machina partners defined in the Consortium Agreement (CA) their background knowledge bringing into the project. Foreground knowledge will be property of the partner generating it. When two or more partners have carried out the design or work, each partner concerned shall have joint ownership of this foreground. In case of transfer ownership of foreground, each partner concerned shall pass on its obligations regarding that foreground to the assignee. In line with the CA, all IP (both background and foreground) within the context of Pop-Machina will be managed under the framework of the project's 'Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan' (i.e. the deliverable at hand), which will be updated at key points of time throughout the project to ensure that relevant activities are aligned to this end and ultimately, pave the way for the smooth exploitation and sustainability of results.

According to the Pop-Machina Grant Agreement (GA) all Pop-Machina partners have agreed to manage IPRs in line with general Commission policies regarding ownership, exploitation rights and confidentiality as described in detail in Section 3 of the GA 'Rights and obligations related to background and results'. Universities or other public research organisations that are part of the consortium must also take measures to implement the principles set out in the Code of Practice annexed to the Commission Recommendation on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities (Points 1 and 2). The basis for IPR management was agreed to be the following:⁹

- background knowledge: any data, know-how or information (tangible or intangible), including intellectual property rights, is held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement, and

6 <http://www.iphandbook.org/handbook/ch05/p01/>

7 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004L0048R%2801%29>

8 European IPR Helpdesk, Fact Sheet IP management in Horizon 2020: at the proposal stage, February 2014.

9 Grant agreement number 821479 — Pop-Machina.

needed to implement the action or exploit the results. All consortium partners will bring in their expertise and knowledge and will retain full ownership of the IPR of this expertise and knowledge. The beneficiaries must identify and agree (in writing) on the background for the action ('agreement on background'). The beneficiaries will provide each other access, under fair and reasonable conditions (including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions) to background needed for exploiting their own results, unless the beneficiary that holds the background has - before acceding to the Agreement - informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel). Pop-Machina partners in the GA have declared that no data, know-how or information shall be needed by another Party for implementation of the Project (Article 25.2 GA) or Exploitation of that other Party's Results (Article 25.3 GA);

- foreground knowledge/results: all newly developed expertise, knowledge and technologies will be owned by the participant(s) in the project that were involved in the development of this specific expertise/technology/methodology. In case several participants have jointly carried out work generating foreground and where their respective share of the work cannot be ascertained, they shall have joint ownership of such foreground. Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them. Two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and if it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection. Depending on the business strategies of the partners involved, they shall either:
 - establish an agreement on transferring the ownership to the partner(s) that is interested in the further exploitation (in this case a fair and reasonable compensation will be provided to the partner transferring ownership);
 - establish an agreement regarding the allocation and terms of exercising that joint ownership.

Furthermore, the Pop-Machina consortium supports open access of scientific publications. In this respect, Pop-Machina will take all necessary actions to ensure free access to peer-reviewed articles resulting from the project. Such actions will include the following routes as these are described in the 'Guidelines on open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon 2020':

1. green open access: deposit an electronic copy of the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication in a scientific publication relating to the project's foreground in an institutional or subject-based repository at the moment of publication. The beneficiaries will make their best efforts to ensure that this electronic copy becomes freely and electronically available to anyone through this repository within 6 months of publication. The exact selection of the repository, the terms under which access will be granted, and all other relevant details will be decided when the publication is available;
2. gold open access: immediately provide in open access mode the article, with the payment of publication costs being shifted away from readers. The costs (Author Processing Charges) will be paid by the partners supporting the research. Partners' budget will be used for open access costs regarding two high-impact papers that the consortium will decide that should be freely available immediately after publication.

Finally, the Pop-Machina consortium supports open access to research data. Regarding the digital research data generated in the action, the beneficiaries must deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate - free of charge for any user - the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible; other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan'. The consortium will also provide information - via the repository - about tools and instruments at the disposal

of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and - where possible - provide the tools and instruments themselves).

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as a field of particular interest

Pop-Machina falls into the GDPR rules in many ways (e.g. processing of personal data). The project is by all means oriented to achieve that personal data are processed fairly and lawfully, obtained only for the specified and lawful purposes and not further processed in any manner incompatible with those purposes, not excessively in relation to the purposes for which they are processed, and not kept for longer than necessary. Moreover, the *Data Management Plan* consecutive deliverables (WP1) thoroughly address all datasets collected, processed or generated. Within all WP where personal data are collected, all GDPR principles for the data collection will be followed and performed with respective actions by the consortium partners. Upon the completion of the project and as required by the regulation, all these personal data will be handled appropriately according to the project management plan. Also, certainly, Pop-Machina will implement all principles of GDPR in its future market operation.

2.5 IP management

Pop-Machina involves a large number of stakeholders as well as a number of different technologies, products, services, methodologies, etc. As early as in the proposal stage, twelve exploitable assets had been identified whilst more are being identified as the project progresses. Pop-Machina is therefore expected to make use, as well as generate a high amount of innovative intellectual assets. The goal is to correctly and timely identify all existing or potential intellectual assets, and at the same time assess their value and benefits. Assets that are identified as exploitable need to be further investigated as to the appropriate means for their legal protection (e.g. patents) and assessed for probable risks (e.g., litigation, infringement) both internally and externally (i.e., within the consortium and partners' organisations and in the stakeholders' environment). The IP management plan will set procedures, following specific steps to manage the aforementioned needs.

In accordance with the Pop-Machina IP strategy, a methodology will be established that will enable the consortium members, as well as other stakeholders, to manage intellectual assets in a coordinated and informed manner. This methodology involves specific steps - stages that will be continuously monitored throughout the project and adjusted if needed as the project progresses and the need arises. The goal of this methodology is to keep partners informed/educated on IP rights, the project assets identified, notifying the consortium on partners claiming IP rights, and facilitating discussions within the consortium, so as to enable decision making on intellectual assets timely and efficiently. The preliminary principles of these processes are presented in Chapter 6. Some of the steps described have already been initiated and as the project progresses, they will be updated or revised according to the consortium and Pop-Machina's needs.

3. Innovation management strategy

3.1 Innovation management

With a view on addressing innovation management in collaborative environments such as the present project, the concept of innovation must firstly be understood. *‘Innovation is about creating new value people are willing to use and pay for, whereas an innovation strategy is the plan for harnessing for example marketing, operations, finance and R&D to support achieving the competitive goal.’*¹⁰ An innovation strategy shouldn’t be confused with innovation tactics, it is not about setting up ideas. Innovation strategy focuses on drawing an organisation’s aims, goals, and value proposition for specific markets. Boundaries to the innovation performance expectations are set by structuring work and making it simple so as to accomplish the best potential outcome.

The innovation strategy sets up an explicit roadmap to succeed in the goals defined by an organisation. These innovation goals should nonetheless not be separated from the organisation’s objectives given that integrated business and innovation goals increase operational efficiency.

The need for innovation thus leads organisations to set long-term innovative goals that as a result lead to alternative to traditional management structures and develop emerging economic sectors. The main contributing factors that necessitate innovation include, amongst others, technological advantages, competition increase and changes in consumer preferences.

Organisations should also examine innovation not only as a market opportunity but also in relation to the commercial relationships that can support its viability. This is nonetheless a challenging process as it is affected by the innovation’s macroenvironment including the general and IP legal framework, current financial circumstances and support mechanisms, the competitive environment, etc.

The main activities that may support innovation activities and process from the generation of an idea stage to the market uptake include the following:

- the idea generation phase that may lead to a new product, process or service;
- the knowledge acquisition phase as a result of ideas generated and;
- the idea realisation phase when the idea is implemented and monitored for market uptake.¹¹

The stages of innovation development in terms of technology, R&D and innovation management can be described in the following figure:

¹⁰ <https://www.viima.com/blog/innovation-strategy>

¹¹ <https://www.5g-mobix.com/assets/files/5G-MOBIX-D1.3-Innovation-Management-Plan-V1.0.pdf>

Figure 3. Management phases of innovation development

Models that follow the approach of innovation management do not concentrate only in developing innovation but focus mainly on the development of collaborative production circular innovation management strategies under diverse social, economic and educational environments. The innovation management within the Pop-Machina includes the design of strategic objectives related to innovation, identification of innovation margins, customer segmentation based on their needs, the required technology for novel ideas, planning of the activities to achieve the technologies, allocation of the resources (both human, financial and technical) to execute the identified activities, and extensive market research to measure the respective market capacity. Tasks of innovation management include the following:

1. identify potential customers other than those that are already in the consortium;
2. target these customers with marketing activities that specifically addresses their needs such as the new circular Pop-Machina solutions;
3. carry out SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities Threats) analysis to identify the competitive advantages of proposed solutions;
4. identify suitable advertising and promotional plans and;
5. exploit the technology through the consortium's SMEs (small-medium-sized enterprises) and larger companies, by developing and following the business strategies developed in WP6.

Pop-Machina has appointed as an Innovation and Sustainability Manager, Mrs Maroulla Schiza from ETAM SA, who is a member and reports to the Executive Board. The Project Innovation and Sustainability Manager is responsible for identifying and promoting innovation opportunities in the project as well as for ensuring the value of project outcomes towards commercialisation and sustainability of pilot cases. She will use adequate processes and tools to collect the appropriate data for planning and executing the innovation plans of the project, and to encourage team members to undertake small-scale innovations that ensure a continuous flow of new opportunities. She is also responsible to monitor the project to guarantee consistency between technical and marketing choices.

3.2 Innovation strategy

Some of the fundamental activities to be developed in this and any innovative process are as follows: Amongst the fundamental activities of any innovative process to be developed include:

- the generation of ideas for new products or processes;
- gaining knowledge from the ideas generated and;
- implementing new products and processes;
- monitoring customer satisfaction.

Innovation management within European projects as a process, requires an extensive understanding of the market as well as the technical problems. The goal of Innovation management is the successful implementation of appropriate creative ideas.

Relative business models and process innovations have a key role in creating, adapting, and maintaining a product or service to market maturity. They are very often triggered through technological innovations, which act as enablers, but also generate requirements for the development of technology.

The Innovation Manager will provide guidance to the consortium with regard to the best practices on innovation management, such as:

- implementation and coordination of innovation management throughout the project;
- the identification of innovation enablers and barriers;
- continuous assessment and revision if necessary, of the innovation management processes;
- identification and monitoring of the project assets that are most promising for market success;
- recognise externalities that may be exploited to create spillover effect.

Innovation does not just require new technologies and products, but also new business models. In the European knowledge economy, production and services are based on knowledge-intensive activities. These activities contribute to an accelerated pace of technical and scientific advance.

Through the project we will use new tools and strategies to accelerate innovation such as:

- circular business support and acceleration services;
- value chain positioning;
- digital collaboration for innovation;
- analysis of customer/user needs;
- brand management;
- (open) innovation management;
- the Pop-Machina Circular Maker Accelerator (training programme).

3.3 Innovation potential

Innovation potential as already identified in Pop-Machina proposal focuses on:

- Urban planning and policy making

The ecosystem approach and the responsive circular makerspace Pop-Machina repurposes makerspaces to support multipurpose community production. The main advantage of this new approach is that if successful this network approach will make the city more responsive to change, either due to societal and circular challenges or due to a change in priorities, resources, flows, and needs. Embedding big data solutions into urban planning will monitor circular production and provide easy to understand visualisations to assist collaborative production governance. Such capabilities are impossible to be achieved with today's production setup and data governance and it can provide city authorities with a powerful tool to understand, assess and manage production and reduce the mistakes of overestimating or underestimating flows. Demonstrating innovative collaborative production and local governance taps in the creativity of citizens (often from non-traditional segments of the population) and modern technology to create new circular community production solutions and provide validation for these solutions. Innovation in persuasive technology can unlock new technology-based services achieving thus positive behavioural change and regulate consumption but also unlocking the market of behavioural change support tools in developing successful community makers.

- Circular collaborative production

Factory of the Future technologies in maker community production will hopefully open the way for a brand-new channel of exploitation for these technologies. Occupational Safety and Health

functionalities in our project and risk mitigation in the makers' communities are also considered to be elemental innovations of the Project.

Finally, cryptography in the maker value chain through blockchain and tokenisation holds an interesting potential for collaborative production that can benefit the ecosystem while providing more space for innovation.

During the lifetime of the project further high potential innovations are expected to be identified that are either directly related to the previously mentioned innovations potential or result as an outcome of the project. These will be carefully identified and monitored mainly by enhancing the consortium's understanding of innovation and frequent communication of achieved results.

4. Markets relevant to Pop-Machina

Awareness on circular economy in Europe and globally is constantly increasing. Circular economy is considered an opportunity for our society to increase prosperity, reducing at the same time its dependency on energy and primary resources, by offering the potential to improve decision making on their use and provide added value for business. At the same time, it offers a secure route to society-wide prosperity and environmental sustainability for future generations. Additionally, following sustainable principles, circular economy can create new job opportunities. According to a research of the Helen MacArthur Foundation¹² apart from the social and environmental benefits of circular economy, a net economic benefit of €1.8 trillion could be generated in Europe by 2030.

Europe's growing economy is based on the focus that has been given for improving resource productivity. Nonetheless resource productivity is still underexploited as a source of wealth, competitiveness, and renewal. According to the same study combining circular economy, with emerging technological solutions, Europe's resource productivity could grow annually by up to 3%. This would generate a primary-resource benefit of as much as €0.6 trillion per year by 2030 to Europe's economies, whilst it would also generate €1.2 trillion in non-resource and externality benefits, bringing the annual total benefits to around €1.8 trillion. In GDP terms this is translated into an increase of up to 7% with a respective employment positive impact.

The EC Circular Economy Package¹³ (2015) includes legislative proposals on waste and a detailed action plan with measures covering the whole material cycle: from production and consumption to waste management and the market for secondary raw materials. At the same time EU's target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 80-95% by 2050 requires fundamental changes in energy, food and mobility systems, as well in processes raw materials and manufactured products are produced, traded, used, maintained and fed back into the economy at the end of their life. Both policies contribute to 'closing the loop' of product life-cycles and apart from bringing benefits for the environment, they have a positive impact in the economy.

Nonetheless the European economy remains wasteful in its model of value creation. We are currently using 16 tonnes of materials annually per person, out of which 6 tonnes become waste.¹⁴ More specifically in 2016, total waste generated in the EU by all economic activities including households came up to 2,538 million tonnes.¹⁵ Constructions were the main contributor of waste production (36.4% of waste produced), followed by mining and quarrying (25.3%), manufacturing (10.3%), waste and water services (10.0%) and households (8.5%), services (4.6%) and energy (3.1%). Just in terms of household waste alone, each person in Europe is currently producing, on average, half of tonne of such waste. Only 40% of it is reused or recycled and in some countries more than 80% still goes to landfill.

Even though waste management is continuously improving in the EU, the European economy is still losing a significant amount of potential 'secondary raw materials' such as metals, wood, glass, paper, plastics present waste streams. In the EU-28 (2016), 2,312 million tonnes of waste were treated. The quantity of waste recovered, that is recycled, or used for backfilling or incinerated with energy recovery grew from 960 million tonnes in 2004 to 1,231 million tonnes in 2016. The quantity of waste

¹² Growth within: a circular economy vision for a competitive Europe, the Helen MacArthur Foundation, 2015.

¹³ European Commission, 2016. Briefing on 'Circular economy package, four legislative proposals on waste'.

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/index.htm>

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Waste_statistics

subject to disposal decreased by 6.3%, that is from 1,154 million tonnes in 2004 to 1,081 million tonnes in 2016. The share of disposal in total waste treatment decreased from 54.6% in 2004 to 46.8% in 2016.

This model of production and use of products and resources costs Europe €7.2 trillion every year for the sectors of mobility, food, and the built environment. More specifically, actual resource costs amount up to €1.8 trillion, other related cash costs (i.e. other household and government expenditures) are €3.4 trillion and externalities (i.e. traffic congestion, carbon, pollution, and noise) amount €2.0 trillion.¹⁶

Recently (March, 2020), the European Commission adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan¹⁷ which includes measures along the entire life cycle of products. The new Action Plan aims to make our economy fit for a green future, strengthen our competitiveness, and at the same time protecting the environment and giving new rights to consumers. Building on the work done since 2015, the new Plan focuses on the design and production for a circular economy, ensuring that the resources used, are maintained in the EU. The plan and the initiatives therein, integrally involve all relevant stakeholders. The main measures of the new Circular Economy Action Plan, which is part of the EU Industrial Strategy, include the following:

- *make sustainable products the norm in the EU*: in order to ensure that products placed on the EU market are sustainable (i.e. designed to last longer, easier to reuse, repair and recycle, and incorporate as much as possible recycled material instead of primary raw material) the Commission will propose legislation on Sustainable Product Policy. To this end ‘single-use’ will be limited, premature obsolescence managed, and the destruction of unsold durable goods will be banned;
- *empower consumers*: issues such as the reparability and durability of products will be accessible to consumers so as to allow them to make environmentally sustainable choices. Consumers will benefit from the ‘Right to Repair’.
- *focus on sectors using most resources and have high circularity potential*: the Commission will launch actions on:
 - electronics and ICT - the ‘Circular Electronics Initiative’ aiming at longer product lifetimes, and improving the collection and treatment of waste;
 - batteries and vehicles - a regulatory framework to enhance their sustainability and circularity;
 - packaging - mandatory requirements on the reduction of (over)packaging and what is allowed on the EU market;
 - plastics - mandatory requirements for recycled content and microplastics, biobased and biodegradable plastics;
 - textiles - an EU Strategy to strengthen competitiveness and innovation and boost textile reuse;
 - construction and buildings - a Strategy for a Sustainably Built Environment, promoting circularity principles;
 - food - legislative initiative on reusable products in food services to substitute single-use packaging, tableware, and cutlery;
- *ensure less waste*: the focus will be on avoiding waste altogether and transforming it into high-quality secondary resources that benefit from a well-functioning market for secondary raw materials. The separate collection of waste and labelling will be explored and a series of actions to minimise EU exports of waste and tackle illegal shipments will be taken.

A circular economy is necessary to achieve climate-neutrality by 2050 and to strengthen European economic competitiveness. Today, European economy is still mostly linear. Only 12%¹⁸ of secondary materials and resources are being brought back into the economy whilst the lifecycle of many prod-

16 <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/sustainability/our-insights/europes-circular-economy-opportunity>

17 https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_420

18 https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_420

ucts is limited. Pop-Machina offers a huge potential to be exploited both for businesses and consumers to transform the way products are made and empower makers and consumers to make sustainable choices.

4.1 The maker movement¹⁹

Over the last decade, communities engaged in do-it-yourself (DIY) activities worldwide have demonstrated an unprecedented regeneration. This came in place by hobbyists, engineers, artists, designers, hackers, and craftsmen, exploring new ways for personal expression by hacking and remaking. This is known as the ‘maker movement’ where the concept behind it is that anyone can and should have access to the tools and knowledge necessary to build anything they might need or want.

The maker movement is about the people’s needs to engage with products in ways that make them more than just consumers. It also stands out as a self-empowering vision where the creation and learning process is of extreme value. In this sense, it is expected that the maker movement will give rise to new forms of education and perhaps employment. An enabling factor for the development of the movement is the increasing availability and affordability of digital fabrication tools such as 3D printers and laser cutters which makes them available to (almost) everyone. The term ‘maker movement’ is still subject of open discussion and may be used with some variants. It could for example refer to hacking activities (the term of ‘hacking’ or ‘hacker’ has expanded from the computer sense into the hacking of physical objects) mainly related to electronics and robotics, or to traditional arts and crafts activities related to woodworking and metalworking.

FabLabs, Hackerspaces and Makerspaces are the physical representations of the maker movement. They seek to offer to communities, businesses, and entrepreneurs the infrastructures and manufacturing equipment necessary to help them transform their ideas and concepts into reality. Even though these community-oriented spaces would appear to have similar structure and use, they have significant distinctions.

FabLabs are workshops, where re-creation and assembly of products takes place, normally use unused, discarded, or broken electronics and raw materials to custom build objects. They all maintain the same hardware and software capabilities, making it possible for people and projects to be easily distributed across them. FabLabs are supported by a global FabLab association, uptaking the dissemination of the FabLab concept and establishing connection between the FabLabs around the world. FabLabs are typically set up in the context of an institution.

Hackerspaces are typically community-funded and community-managed spaces. The terms ‘hacking’ and ‘hacker’ go beyond programming activities and include physical prototyping and electronics. Hackerspaces have a unique organisation, structure, ideology, and focus. They provide the hardware tools and manufacturing equipment, as well as the learning environment and the necessary support for individuals to develop their projects. They are completely independent, although collaboration between spaces is quite common.

The concept for Makerspaces refers to any generic space (often including FabLabs and Hackerspaces) that promotes active participation, knowledge sharing, and collaboration among individuals through open exploration and creative use of technology. Makerspaces do not comply with a pre-defined structure or a pre-defined set of fabrication tools. Makerspaces focus on having a publicly accessible creative space that explores the maker mind-set and tinkering practices.

According to the ‘Overview of the maker movement in the European Union. Publications Office of the European Union’ (Rosa et al., 2017) the maker movement in Europe is not a homogeneous movement, both in terms of spatial distribution and identity. In this study two types of makerspaces were mainly identified, FabLabs and Hackerspaces. Noticeably, the absolute number of FabLabs and

¹⁹ Rosa, P., Ferretti, F., Guimarães Pereira, Â., Panella, F., & Wanner, M. (2017). Overview of the maker movement in the European Union. Publications Office of the European Union.

Hackerspaces is relatively close, with 397 FabLabs (48%) being identified against 327 Hackerspaces (40%). Western Europe countries have a higher number of makerspaces with France, Germany and Italy accounting for more than half of the makerspaces in EU28. All major capital cities in EU28 were found to have at least one makerspace, illustrating the spatial spread of the movement. It was observed that the main thematic areas of interest are very similar among the various spaces. 546 makerspaces indicated interest in digital fabrication, 273 in programming and 247 in electronics. Topics related to design, arts and education were also frequent.

The economic sustainability of a makerspace was found to be greatly dependent on secured funding (i.e. sponsorships), and sources of income. The most common sources of income are membership fees (flat - monthly or annual payment - or varied - based on the use of the makerspace); or via the payment of a fee based on the equipment usage time or material consumed. Overall, 335 makerspaces were identified with a membership scheme (72%); 73 makerspaces (16%) with a payment scheme based on equipment usage or material consumed; and 55 makerspaces (12%) with no fee at all.

The different membership rates applied across the EU28 countries ranged from an average of 4.2 €/month in Malta to an average of 43.2 €/month in the Netherlands. The European average was of 20.93 €/month.

4.2 Distributed production and collaborative technologies

An increasing trend and need for decentralised production structures is rising. Modern organisational models for small, flexible and scalable manufacturing units in distributed production networks are needed to satisfy individual customer needs and sustainability in the supply chain. Distributed production, is a form of decentralised manufacturing practiced by enterprises using a network of geographically dispersed manufacturing facilities that are coordinated using information technology.²⁰

Contrary to past efforts for the establishment of decentralised production units to low-cost countries, today efforts focus on distributed productions with the aim of a global market development that meets local needs. Innovative production concepts replace traditional network structures towards a personalised ‘mass customisation’.

The concept of sustainability in production is gaining in importance, and the value and benefit for customers is in the foreground. The satisfaction of a demand under creation of value in a socially and environmentally responsible manner is becoming a major objective. A decentralised network of adaptable and flexible small production units may lead to reduced CO₂ emissions through reduction of transports, serving at the same time regional development.²¹

Distributed manufacturing allows small - and large - scale production through information networks that aggregate and coordinate production systems. It can also be much more direct, using algorithms to enable peer-to-peer coordination and exchange. The involvement of many intermediaries of the typical manufacturing supply chains is shifted to the information layer.

The future of the distributed production is in platforms and other *collaborative technologies* that integrate and coordinate manufacturing. They provide connectivity for the integration of diverse components and form an infrastructure of reusable tools and functions for developers to easily build applications on. They operate as two-sided markets for service providers and end users, incorporating data, logic, and connectivity with standardised protocols that connect technologies for production and exchange. Platforms provide the means of governance for producers who create their products and consumers who use them.

Decentralised web technologies are the key infrastructure enabling the formation of truly decentralised ecosystems of manufacturing. Blockchain technology enables system - wide visibility across supply chains allowing companies to meet the transparency, traceability, accountability, and efficiency

²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distributed_manufacturing

²¹ Mattab D., Raucha E., Dallasegaa P., Trends towards Distributed Manufacturing Systems and modern forms for their design, 2015.

requirements for competitiveness. It provides the infrastructure that allows companies to link physical goods to serial numbers and digital tags and record them on a shared platform.

The use of token economies can radically reshape the financing of manufacturing, by pushing focus of value and production from the individual producers to whole supply chain. Tokenising the exchange of value along a supply chain, blockchain networks can work to re-empower the producers that are active in the system. The major advantage of token economics supply chains is that they can become self-financing systems that do not depend on the interests of external financiers.

Smart contracts are another basic element for distributed production that can make it possible to integrate basic routine procedures and operations within a manufacturing network. Using smart contract technology, any buyer on the blockchain can access the contract, confirm manufacturer's quality and reputation and using an automated discovery process. Unlike classic contracts, a smart contract can automatically negotiate prices, thus reducing costs and improving transaction speed.²²

Long - established production methods will continue to change so as to satisfy the demand for individuality and customer-specific product variants. Therefore, the concept of the Distributed Manufacturing plays an increasingly important role. New and innovative ways of production organisation will be necessary driven by the need for a sustainable and ecologically production and distribution. Small, flexible, and scalable production units (mini-factories) in decentralised production networks that adjust to the local and individual customer needs, producing at a local level are the way forward.

In order to enable innovation in collaborative technologies, focus should be given on establishing a proper legal and regulatory framework, being a fiscal, licensing and intellectual property framework that supports collaboration. At European level, initiatives and investments in cross-sector innovation are important enabling factors. World Economic Forum²³ research indicates that tax, trade and procurement regulations often impact the establishment of innovative technological collaborations. Public-sector funds can also be instrumental in encouraging collaborations, while policies around data security and data privacy are critical regulatory elements in the digital economy.

²² <https://systemsinnovation.io/distributed-manufacturing-how-it-works/>

²³ Collaborative Innovation Transforming Business, Driving Growth, WEF World Economic Forum, 2015.

5. Project assets

In the Horizon 2020 programme project results are defined as:

‘Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.’

(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

To ensure the effective exploitation of Pop-Machina’s results, all of the partners were carefully selected based on their expertise, potential, and complementarity with each other. The Pop-Machina cities (Leuven, Thessaloniki, Piraeus, Santander, Venlo, Istanbul, Kaunas) have the political and operational power and capacity to fully exploit project results after the project ends. The academic and research partners (KU Leuven, UOM, UNICAN, TU DELFT, ISM, KU, UC, LAW, CERTH, IAAC) are interested in acquiring evidence-based knowledge from real cases, as it will lead to scientific publications and it will further exploit project’s assets in follow-up projects. Technology providing partners (CERTH, INTRA) will have the chance to fully test and demonstrate their technologies in new application fields, leading to the creation of new markets and opportunities for further technological applications. Finally, consultancies and SME partners (ETAM, Q-PLAN, WR, PLANET) will actively seek to exploit methodologies, structures, and tools for supporting circular endeavors both of the private and public sector (e.g. municipal, regional).

Project assets, as identified per partner in the proposal are presented in the following table. These assets and results were updated through an open process (see next chapter) and were revised by partners. New assets were identified and classified as per their exploitation potential (scientific, commercial, non-commercial). The revised project assets are also provided in the following tables.

Table 2. Project assets per partner

Pop-Machina Assets		City Partners							
ASSET	BRIEF EXPLANATION	LEUVEN (BE)	THESS (GR)	PIR (GR)	SCC (SP)	VENLO (NL)	IMM (TR)	ISTAC (TR)	KAUNAS (LT)
Pop-Machina urban development framework	1. The POP-MACHINA novel urban development framework consisting of new urban planning approaches and tools, driven by circular maker ecosystems	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Circular Maker Communities	2. The POP-MACHINA Circular Maker Communities that will be set-up during the project with the objective to contribute to the local circular collaborative economy, during and beyond the project's lifecycle	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Circular Makerspaces	3. The regenerated POP-MACHINA Circular Makerspaces developed within the pilot cities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	4. The POP-MACHINA Maker Academy that will consist of a fast paced and practical training programme tailored for circular making and innovation	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social collaboration platform	5. The integrated social collaboration platform that builds upon FoF technologies and will assist community cooperation, knowledge sharing, data collection and analysis, including also gamification and supporting OHS.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Online inventory	6. The online inventory of circular maker solutions for sharing of circular and regenerative best practices	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Circular product / service prototypes	7. The circular product/service prototypes developed and demonstrated by the communities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	8. The co-created Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework, with the accompanying toolkit, for urban and peri-urban circularity and regenerative capacity, including technical indicators, as well as social, sustainability and scalability variables.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
BaaS mechanism	9. The Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism for smart contracts and circularity certification								
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	10. The tokenisation and incentivisation schemes for behavioural change, motivation and engagement	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Pop-Machina Accelerator	11. The POP-MACHINA Accelerator with its business development and circular innovation support services that will fuel circular entrepreneurship								
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	12. The POP-MACHINA Integration Guide including practical pathways for the adoption of the project's tools, methods and production cases by relevant authorities, to spread circular collaborative production across Europe	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Pop-Machina Assets		Academic and Research Partners										Technology Providing Partners		Consultancies and SME Partners			
ASSET	BRIEF EXPLANATION	KUL (BE)	UC (UK)	LAW (GR)	UNICAN (SP)	UOM (GR)	TUDELFT (NL)	KU (TR)	ISM (LT)	CERTH (GR)	IAAC (SP)	CERTH (GR)	INTRA (LU)	ETAM (GR)	Q-PLAN (GR)	WR (BE)	PLANET (TR)
Pop-Machina urban development framework	1. The POP-MACHINA novel urban development framework consisting of new urban planning approaches and tools, driven by circular maker ecosystems	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X
Circular Maker Communities	2. The POP-MACHINA Circular Maker Communities that will be set-up during the project with the objective to contribute to the local circular collaborative economy, during and beyond the project's lifecycle	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Circular Makerspaces	3. The regenerated POP-MACHINA Circular Makerspaces developed within the pilot cities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	4. The POP-MACHINA Maker Academy that will consist of a fast paced and practical training programme tailored for circular making and innovation	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X
Social collaboration platform	5. The integrated social collaboration platform that builds upon FoF technologies and will assist community cooperation, knowledge sharing, data collection and analysis, including also gamification and supporting OHS.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
Online inventory	6. The online inventory of circular maker solutions for sharing of circular and regenerative best practices	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X
Circular product / service prototypes	7. The circular product/service prototypes developed and demonstrated by the communities													X	X	X	X
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	8. The co-created Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework, with the accompanying toolkit, for urban and peri-urban circularity and regenerative capacity, including technical indicators, as well as social, sustainability and scalability variables.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X
BaaS mechanism	9. The Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism for smart contracts and circularity certification	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	10. The tokenisation and incentivisation schemes for behavioural change, motivation and engagement	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X						
Pop-Machina Accelerator	11. The POP-MACHINA Accelerator with its business development and circular innovation support services that will fuel circular entrepreneurship	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	12. The POP-MACHINA Integration Guide including practical pathways for the adoption of the project's tools, methods and production cases by relevant authorities, to spread circular collaborative production across Europe	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X

6. Preliminary strategies for exploitation and sustainability

6.1 Exploitation

Exploitation of project results refers to making use of these results during and after the project implementation - for commercial purposes, in further research activities, to improve policies, and/or or tackling economic and societal problems - by project partners or end-users.

Even though the exploitation of results can occur during the project, exploitation is usually more relevant towards the end of a project when the bulk of expected outcomes typically surface. Note that partners have the obligation (according to the GA) to exploit results generated by the project for a period of up to four years after the completion of the project taking measures that directly aim to ensure ‘exploitation’ either directly or indirectly (in particular through transfer or licensing). An exploitation plan should start early on in a project, be ‘alive’ and adapt throughout the project, according to its need and also be able to exploit project results beyond its completion. Protection of results is also crucial given that an effective exploitation depends on it. To this end, Pop-Machina results must be assessed once these are generated, identified, and evaluated in the context of IP Strategy. As mentioned in chapter 2, Pop-Machina has over the proposal stage and grant preparation phase, identified and analysed several IP rights, that are significant for the Project’s IPR Strategy. The steps that follow regard the determination of the methodology that is going to be followed, to carry out the implementation phase, and project conclusion phase.

The exploitation plan should also be aligned with the project’s business and marketing plan. The elaboration of a business plan for the most promising circular productions piloted within the project will be a key exploitation mechanism that will assist their further development, access to finance and market uptake.

Therefore, the steps that need to be taken to gradually build the project’s exploitation of results are as follows:

6.1.1 Identification of the project assets

The phase was officially initiated on the 27th of February 2020, when project partners were invited to identify the project’s exploitable results via email communications. An excel file was attached containing project’s exploitable assets/results that were identified in the Pop-Machina proposal’s preliminary assessment. The goal was for partners to verify within the same file whether they agree with the breakdown of exploitable assets per partner and identify any further exploitable assets. Additionally, to enable partners to perceive the concepts of project assets and exploitation respective definitions were provided and examples of other possible exploitable assets were included in the communication.

An additional breakdown of exploitable assets was presented namely commercial, non-commercial and academic in order to produce the preliminary categorisation of assets for IP management purposes.

All partners provided their feedback and a few new exploitable assets emerged are described at the end of this section.

City partners

Table 3. Stad Leuven assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Non-commercial
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Circular product/service prototypes	Non-commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
BaaS mechanism	Non-commercial
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Accelerator	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Non-commercial
Publications	Non-commercial
Training course	Non-commercial
Follow-up research	Non-commercial
Market analysis	Non-commercial
Policy change	Non-commercial
Business plan	Non-commercial
Data	Non-commercial

Table 4. Dimos Thessalonikis assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Non-commercial
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Circular product/service prototypes	Non-commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
BaaS mechanism	Non-commercial
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Non-commercial

Table 5. Dimos Peiraia assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Scientific
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Scientific
Social collaboration platform	Scientific
Online inventory	Scientific
Circular product/service prototypes	Commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Commercial
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Scientific
Publications	Scientific
Training course	Non-commercial

Table 6. Ayuntamiento De Santander assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Non-commercial
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Circular product/service prototypes	Non-commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
BaaS mechanism	Non-commercial
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Accelerator	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Non-commercial
Dissemination through cities networks	

Table 7. Gemeente Venlo assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Scientific
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Scientific
Social collaboration platform	Scientific
Online inventory	Scientific
Circular product/service prototypes	Commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Commercial
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Scientific
Publications	Scientific
Training course	Non-commercial

Table 8. Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Non-commercial
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
Standards	Non-commercial
Training course	Non-commercial
Policy change	Non-commercial

Table 9. ISTAC Istanbul Cevre Yonetim Sanayive Ticaret assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Circular product/service prototypes	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Non-commercial
Training course	Non-commercial

Table 10. Kauno Miesto Savivaldybes Administracija assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Circular product/service prototypes	Non-commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Non-commercial

Academic and research partners

Table 11. Katholieke Universiteit Leuven KU Leuven assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Non-commercial
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Non-commercial
Publications	Scientific
Training course	Commercial
Designs/Design studies	Scientific
Licences	Non-commercial
Video	Non-commercial
Business plan	Commercial
Data	Scientific
Method	Scientific
Indicators	Scientific
Map	Scientific

Table 12. The Chancellor Masters and Scholars of the University of Cambridge UCAM assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Scientific
Publications	Scientific

Table 13. Commonlawgic make assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Non-commercial
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Scientific
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Scientific
Social collaboration platform	Scientific
Online inventory	Non-commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Scientific
BaaS mechanism	Scientific
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Scientific
Pop-Machina Accelerator	Scientific
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Scientific
Publications, Lectures, Advisory	Non-commercial
Standards	Scientific
Service	Scientific
Trademarks	Scientific
Patents	Scientific
Follow-up research	Scientific
Demonstrators and prototypes	Scientific
Designs/Design studies	Scientific
Market analysis	Scientific
Licences	Scientific
Transfer agreements	Scientific
Policy change	Non-commercial
Products and/or services	Scientific
Business plan	Scientific
Start-ups/Joint ventures	Scientific
Data	Non-commercial
Method	Non-commercial

Table 14. Universidad de Cantabria UNICAN assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Non-commercial
BaaS mechanism	Scientific
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Scientific
Publications	Scientific
Follow-up research	Scientific
Demonstrators and prototypes	Non-commercial
On-line inventory of secondary raw material	Non-commercial

Table 15. University of Macedonia assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Circular product/service prototypes	

Table 16. Technische Universiteit Delft assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Scientific
Circular Maker Communities	Scientific
Circular Makerspaces	Scientific
Social collaboration platform	Scientific
Online inventory	Scientific
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Scientific
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Scientific

Table 17. KOC University assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Social collaboration platform	Scientific
Publications	Scientific
Training course	Non-commercial
Follow-up research	Scientific
Exploration of circular design solutions and process	Scientific
Data about local makers, collaboration and interaction frequencies in the platform	Scientific
Tailored and new co-creation methodologies	Scientific

Table 18. ISM Vadybos Ir Ekonomikos Universitetas assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	
Circular Maker Communities	
Circular Makerspaces	
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	
Social collaboration platform	
Online inventory	
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	
BaaS mechanism	
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	
Pop-Machina Accelerator	
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	

Table 19. Institut d'Arquitectura Avancada de Catalunya IAAC assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Non-commercial
Publications	Scientific
Training Course	Commercial
Designs/Design studies	Scientific
Licences	Non-Commercial
Business plan	Commercial

Technology providing partners

Table 20. Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Scientific
Circular Maker Communities	Scientific
Circular Makerspaces	Scientific
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Scientific
Social collaboration platform	Commercial
Online inventory	Scientific
Circular product/service prototypes	Commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Scientific
BaaS mechanism	Scientific
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Scientific

Table 21. Intrasoft International SA assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
BaaS mechanism	Commercial
Sustainable heterogeneous data collection and analysis tool	Commercial

Consultancies and SME partners

Table 22. ETAM SA Consulting Services assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Scientific
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Commercial
Evaluation and impact assessment methodology	Non-commercial

Table 23. Q-PLAN International Advisors PC assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Business plan	

Table 24. White Research SPRL assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina urban development framework	Scientific
Circular Maker Communities	Non-commercial
Circular Makerspaces	Non-commercial
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	Commercial
Social collaboration platform	Non-commercial
Online inventory	Scientific
Circular product/service prototypes	Commercial
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	Scientific
BaaS mechanism	Commercial
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme	Scientific
Pop-Machina Accelerator	Commercial
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	Non-commercial

Table 25. Planet Turkey Yonetim Ve Gelistirme Danismanlik Anonim Sirekti assets and types of exploitations

Pop-Machina asset	Type of exploitation
Pop-Machina Accelerator	Commercial
Market analysis	Commercial
Products and/or services	Commercial
Business plan	Commercial

This process apart from the reevaluation of project assets per partner resulted on a number of new expected results. These assets will be presented to the consortium and partners will reclaim rights based on their exploitation expectations, taking into account whether they own the respective asset rights (see Section 6.1.2).

- publications;
- standards;
- training course;
- trademarks;
- patents;
- follow-up research;
- demonstrators and prototypes;
- designs/design studies;
- market analysis;
- licences;
- transfer agreements;
- policy change;
- products and/or services;
- business plan;
- start-ups/joint ventures;
- data;
- method;
- indicators;
- map;

- video;
- on-line inventory of secondary raw material;
- exploration of circular design solutions and process;
- data about local makers, collaboration and interaction frequencies in the platform;
- tailored and new co-creation methodologies;
- evaluation and impact assessment methodology;
- sustainable heterogeneous data collection and analysis tool.

Note that as the project progresses potential user groups and more exploitable assets will be identified, or partners may realise that an asset already identified concerns them or even that they wish to exploit it in different ways. To this end, these tables will be updated, following the same process. Scheduling will follow the revised versions of the Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan deliverables.

6.1.2 Finalisation of project assets and IP management and rights

After this stage and having identified all possible assets, IP management and rights will be tackled. Partners will again be asked to provide input using an updated file to claim IP rights per identified asset. Specific IPR issues such as confidentiality, ownership, access rights, responsibilities will be discussed with partners in person-to-person meetings or in the form of questionnaires. Additionally, rights on background agreements that took place during the GA phase will be reevaluated so as to further value the IP background offered by partners as the project progresses.

The following template will be used to initiate IP rights management:

Figure 4. IPR management template

Result/asset number						
Result/asset title						
		Partner 1	Partner 2	Partner 3	Partner 4
1	Partners willing to go to the market					
2	Porte-parole partner (not contributing)					
3	Partners providing background knowledge willing to claim rights					
4	Partners providing background knowledge NOT willing to claim rights					
5	Partners providing results/foreground knowledge willing to claim rights					
6	Partners providing results/foreground knowledge NOT willing to claim rights					
Put an X where appropriate						

6.1.3 Decide upon exploitable assets and particular rights

After this preliminary process is completed a number of key issues will need to be addressed. A key issue is to determine which of the identified results will be actually exploitable (i.e. using SWOT analysis tool), as well as which IP management measures need to be taken per asset. Additionally, in case of joint ownership of results, management of exploitation activities will need to be addressed and even examine the terms under which the results can be exploited outside the project. IP risks will also be recorded, and mitigation strategies will be proposed. These issues, will be further investigated

and analysed within the next version of the Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan and will be concluded in the Replication and Integration Guides of the Pop-Machina results (M48), based on the Pop-Machina’s stakeholders needs, as these will be identified and evaluated during the course of the project.

6.2 Sustainability

The strategic target of all dissemination, communication and exploitation activities of Pop-Machina is to pave the way towards the widespread adoption and sustainability of its results beyond the end of the grant, thus maximising their impact. This constitutes a major priority and challenge for our consortium, given the high potential that the project’s results hold for bringing the EU into the fore-front of circular regeneration. The main challenge of the project and its pilots is connecting sustainability with collaborative production as it will be implemented through project solutions.

Sustainability is the means to connect long term environmental, societal and economic challenges. Sustainable development focuses on balancing local and global efforts to meet basic human needs, moving forward technologically and economically, without degrading the environment.²⁴ The World Summit on Social Development, back in 2005, identified three core areas of sustainable development environmental - economic - social. The three pillars of sustainability are presented below, each analysed in broad non-extensive topics relative to the respective pillar.²⁵ Circular economy is the policy tool to ensure coherence between these pillars.

Figure 5. Sustainability pillars coherence to circular economy

24 <https://www.environmentalscience.org/sustainability>

25 https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2015-05/documents/sustainability_primer_v9.pdf

These challenges can be assessed by fitting them in a traditional SWOT analysis (internal Strengths - Weaknesses, relative to external Opportunities - Threats) emphasising on sustainability. This approach offers through a traditional tool a ‘common language’ amongst partners and stakeholders for the understanding and evaluation of project’s sustainability.

SWOT analysis is one of the most popular strategic tools that exists today. A SWOT helps organisations to identify their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats and then develop strategies that leverage their strengths to overcome weaknesses and threats. It is a tool that is both effective and simple. The sSWOT (sustainability-SWOT) examines these aspects from a sustainability perspective, offering a comprehensive identification of the broader global trends that have an impact on business performance, climate change, waste production, water and energy usage, air pollution, etc. as well as megatrends such as emerging technologies and the Internet of Things.

Following the typical SWOT methodology, the project will be assessed using the SWOT matrix. The assessment will be based on environmental challenges that are shaping future markets and identify areas where such challenges are creating large, unmet needs in society. The project assets and their main exploitation routes, including sustainable models for the operation of the Circular Makerspaces go beyond the project’s duration.

In the following a preliminary short analysis is presented as an example of the process that will be followed:

<p>Strengths</p> <p><i>How can the project apply its strengths to environmental challenges?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The project’s innovative solutions - High experience of partners in implementation of environmental measures - Guidelines for the implementation of environmental legislation produced within the project - LCA analysis will provide quantified data 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <p><i>What are the problems faced in addressing the environmental challenges or risks that can lead to failure?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long term investments for sustainable development are not scheduled - Legislative framework is not common or equally implemented within the pilot areas - The collaborative economy - social economy framework is not adequately developed - Citizens mentality is not supportive on sustainable development
<p>Opportunities</p> <p><i>Can we create new solutions to address challenges?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public - private partnerships in sustainable development - Implementation of circular certification management schemes - European policy integration and access to markets - Increasing demand of circular products and access to new markets 	<p>Threats</p> <p><i>Are there any challenges that may threaten business value?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legislative framework is being reviewed as the project progresses - Covid-19 crisis may put collaborative activities on hold - Change of focus of policies due to the pandemia’s economic impact - Difficulties in sustainability investment costs

Sustainability assessment will be linked to the project innovations as they will be identified in the assets phase. The assets lay down on project partners’ expertise, so they will uptake the further exploitation of relevant areas of innovations, e.g. Collaborative Production, Circular Economy, Urban Planning & Development, business support, education, public administration and services, etc. Each partner will give feedback on the plans to further exploit the project innovations and the possibility of multiplication of the project results in given sector/s.

sSWOT analysis will focus on the above-listed innovations and after the provided feedback from the individual partners, an analysis of the identified risks and opportunities, strengths and weaknesses will be made.

As the sSWOT can produce a number of insights, the main findings will be prioritised as to their relevance to key environmental challenges and cross referenced to the projects and specific task’s main KPIs (see next chapter). The final step will be to decide upon the actions that need to be taken to maximise sustainability that may be short term (within the project’s lifetime) or long term (beyond

the end of the project and over the exploitation period). In the following figure the steps for a sSWOT analysis are presented following the proposed methodology of the World Resources Institute.

Figure 6. sSWOT analysis²⁶

6.3 Scheduling exploitation and sustainability strategy actions

The following diagram summarises the different actions previously described in a diagrammatic presentation and sets an initial timescheduling.

Figure 7. Exploitation & sustainability strategy process

26 sSWOT A sustainability SWOT, WORLD RESOURCES INSTITUTE, 2012.

7. KPIs

Pop-Machina aims at enhancing the excellence of Europe in the circular economy, and especially circular and regenerative cities, as well as at integrating its outcomes in the relevant fields, i.e. innovation, technology, education, environment, and business. As such, exploitation of the project outcomes by the targeted stakeholders in all sectors of application is one of the foremost concerns of our consortium.

In order to achieve the successful implementation of exploitation activities, and fulfilment of the relevant objectives, a systematic monitoring will be carried out throughout the project implementation.

Regular monitoring will allow the identification of possible risks and deviations from the relative objectives and performance indicators, and the timely planning of any necessary correction actions to address potential implementation problems. Such an approach will improve the overall performance of the relevant activities and enable a more efficient evaluation.

This task aims to ensure that the exploitation and sustainability of the project's results as well as their adoption by other cities. The key performance indicators (KPI) which will be used to evaluate the success of the project's actions as specified by the GA the KPIs that concern this task (8.4) as well as all tasks of WP8 are:

- KPI 25: contribution to EU circular economy action plan: 7 pillars, 5 priority sectors;
- KPI 26: contribution to the habitat III new urban agenda: 5 declarations;
- KPI 27: contribution to the urban agenda for the EU: 7 priority themes.

More specifically the relation of these KPIs with the project's exploitable assets is:

KPI 25: contribution to EU circular economy action plan: 7 pillars, 5 priority sectors

The contribution to the 7 pillars (production, consumption, waste management, market for secondary raw materials, specific priority areas, innovation and investment, progress monitoring) as well as the 5 priority sectors (plastics, food waste, critical raw materials, construction and demolition, biomass and bio-based products) will be succeeded by their implementation within the project by the Pop-Machina pilots and the applications of the Pop-Machina platform. The task will contribute to EU Circular Economy Action Plan by supporting the development and sustainability of maker ecosystems. It will thus ensure the exploitation of results and their sustainability in the aforementioned policy priorities.

The 'Circular Economy Package' and the enclosed '*Circular Economy Action Plan*',²⁷ adopted in December 2015, included a range of specific legislative and other supporting proposals and initiatives with the aim of supporting the transition to a circular economy in Europe. The 7 pillars and 5 priority sectors will be examined in the following as to their relevance to the project assets and on how the project contributes in the implementation of this policy:

Pillar 1: Production

Circular economy starts at the very beginning of a product's life. Both the design phase and production processes have an impact on resource use and waste generation throughout a product's lifecycle. Better design can make products more durable or easier to repair, upgrade or remanufacture. It can

²⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52015DC0614>

help recyclers to disassemble products in order to recover valuable materials and components. Even for products or materials designed in a smart way, inefficient use of resources in production processes can lead to lost business opportunities and significant waste generation.

Pop-Machina's contribution to efficient - circular products design and production processes is achieved by the Maker Academy where stakeholders receive appropriate training tailored for circular making and innovation and the online inventory of circular maker solutions for sharing of circular and regenerative best practices. Additionally, the circular product/service prototypes developed and demonstrated by the communities will provide guidance on circular economy into Best Available Techniques. Finally, product circularity certification is supported by The Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism.

Pillar 2: Consumption

The choices made by consumers may support or hamper circular economy. Their choices may be shaped by information to which consumers have access and the range and prices of existing products. Faced with several labels or environmental claims, consumers find it difficult to differentiate between products and to trust the information available. Green claims may not always meet legal requirements for reliability, accuracy, and clarity.

A series of tools and methodologies for measuring Product Environmental Footprints and communicate environmental information will be developed in the frames of Pop-Machina, such as Data collection and analysis tools and the Evaluation and impact assessment described in WP7. More specifically these are the co-created Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework, with the accompanying toolkit, for urban and peri-urban circularity and regenerative capacity, including technical indicators, as well as social, sustainability and scalability variables, as well as the integrated social collaboration platform that builds upon FoF technologies and will assist community cooperation, knowledge sharing, data collection and analysis, including also gamification and supporting Occupational Health and Safety (OHS). Additionally, the Pop-Machina Integration Guide including practical pathways for the adoption of the project's tools, methods and production cases by relevant authorities, to spread circular collaborative production across Europe will be a helpful tool along with city's individual exploitation plans to enhance circular economy requirements for Green Public Procurement.

Pillar 3: Waste management

Waste management plays a central role in the circular economy. The way we collect and manage our waste can lead either to high rates of recycling and to valuable materials finding their way back into the economy, or to an inefficient system where most recyclable waste ends in landfills or is incinerated, with potentially harmful environmental impacts and significant economic losses.

To this end the project will help in the identification and dissemination of good practices in waste collection systems through the Pop-Machina novel urban development framework consisting of new urban planning approaches and tools, driven by circular maker ecosystems such as alternative waste collection systems. Moreover, the online inventory of circular maker solutions for sharing of circular and regenerative best practices is also supporting this pillar as a way of identification and dissemination of good practice in waste collection systems.

Pillar 4: From waste to resources: boosting the market for secondary raw materials and water reuse

In a circular economy, materials that can be recycled are injected back into the economy as new raw materials thus increasing the security of supply. A key factor in creating a dynamic market for secondary raw materials is sufficient demand, driven by the use of recycled materials in products and infrastructure. Pop-Machina contributes directly to the fourth pillar of the EU Circular Economy Action plan, by increasing the (small) proportion of the secondary raw materials used in the EU. In

particular, it will contribute to the development of secondary raw materials' processing guidelines by means of its monitoring framework and training programmes; it will demonstrate how secondary raw materials can be sourced by geographically proximate urbanised areas; and it will show how the market demand for secondary raw materials can be boosted.

Pillar 5: Priority areas

A number of sectors face specific challenges in the context of the circular economy, because of the specificities of their products or value-chains, their environmental footprint or dependency on materials from outside Europe. The 5 priority sectors include Biomass and biobased products, Construction and demolition, Critical raw materials, Foodwaste and Plastics.

These sectors need to be addressed in a targeted way, to ensure that the interactions between the various phases of the cycle are fully taken into account along the whole value chain. These priority areas are being the focus of action of the Pop-Machina cities and will be highlighted by their individual exploitation plans. The project results will produce the methodology and indicators to measure waste, standards for material-efficient recycling and development of core indicators for the assessment of lifecycle environmental performance.

Pillar 6: innovation, investment, and other horizontal measures

The transition to a circular economy is a systemic change. In addition to targeted actions affecting each phase of the value chain and key sectors, it is necessary to create the conditions under which a circular economy can flourish, and resources can be mobilised. Pop-Machina is developing the framework, as well as a set of tools and methodologies that will drive circular maker ecosystems, boost business development and circular innovation and will provide the Integration Guide pathways for the adoption of the project's tools, methods and production cases by relevant authorities, to spread circular collaborative production across Europe.

Pillar 7: Monitoring progress towards a circular economy

In order to assess progress towards a more circular economy and the effectiveness of action at EU and national level, the action programme requires the adoption of a set of reliable indicators.

Pop-Machina is monitoring a series of KPIs in accordance to the Sustainable Development indicators monitored by EUROSTAT. These indicators are expressed into project assets through the co-created Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework, with the accompanying toolkit, for urban and peri-urban circularity and regenerative capacity, including technical indicators, as well as social, sustainability and scalability variables.

Regarding the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, Pop-Machina adopts an innovative approach both toward the product and services design phase (directly relevant to Sustainable Development Goal 12 for the promotion of sustainable consumption and production patterns), educating makers about how to develop products that are more durable and easier to repair or remanufacture, and toward the production process, identifying and testing more environmentally and socially efficient ways of production.

On the broader level, however, Pop-Machina assets are highly relevant to all pillars of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, as they addresses the issue of circular economy throughout the entire production lifecycle, promote the remodeling of materials of high priority, and activate groundbreaking measures (such as tokenisation) to increase innovation and sustainability of the resulting circular processes.

The following table presents the Pillars that are addressed by the main expected assets of Pop-Machina.

Table 26. Pop-Machina assets per circular economy action plan pillar

Pop-Machina assets	Pillar 1	Pillar 2	Pillar 3	Pillar 4	Pillar 5	Pillar 6	Pillar 7
Pop-Machina urban development framework			x	x		x	
Circular Maker Communities			x			x	
Circular Makerspaces		x	x			x	
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	x			x			
Social collaboration platform				x			x
Online inventory	x	x	x	x			
Circular product/service prototypes	x			x			
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework				x	x		x
BaaS mechanism	x			x	x		
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme				x			
Pop-Machina Accelerator				x		x	
Pop-Machina Integration Guide		x				x	

KPI 26: contribution to the habitat III new urban agenda: 5 declarations

Regarding the *New Urban Agenda*,²⁸ on the *urban stakeholder empowerment side*, Pop-Machina contributes directly to the declaration 41 by ‘promoting enhanced civil engagement and co-provision and coproduction’, as well as to the declarations 154 and 155 by ‘promoting co-production networks between subnational entities, local governments and other relevant stakeholders’ and ‘promoting capacity-development initiatives to empower and strengthen the skills and abilities of women and girls, children and youth, older persons and persons with disabilities, and local communities’.

These declarations will be supported by the Pop-Machina Circular Maker Communities that will be set-up during the project with the objective to contribute to the local circular collaborative economy, and regenerated Pop-Machina Circular Makerspaces developed within the pilot cities. These project assets support enhanced civil engagement and co-provision and coproduction mechanisms. The integrated social collaboration platform will also assist community cooperation and knowledge sharing. Skills empowering and strengthening of local communities will also be supported by the Pop-Machina Maker Academy. The Pop-Machina Integration Guide will promote the adoption of the project’s tools, methods and production cases by relevant authorities, to spread circular collaborative production across Europe.

On the *spatial planning side*, the project contributes to the declarations 51 and 52 by contributing to the development of new ‘*urban spatial frameworks [...] that support sustainable management and use of natural resources and land [...] and enhance resource efficiency, urban resilience and environmental sustainability*’ and ‘*spatial development strategies [...] prioritising urban renewal and [...] preventing urban sprawl and marginalisation*’.

Specifically, the Pop-Machina novel urban development framework consists of new urban planning approaches and tools, driven by circular maker ecosystems whilst urban renewal and prevention of marginalisation is succeeded through the regenerated Pop-Machina Circular Makerspaces developed within the pilot cities.

²⁸ <http://habitat3.org/the-new-urban-agenda/>

Project exploitable assets that are contributing to the Habitat III New Urban Agenda are summarised in the following table:

Table 27. Pop-Machina assets per habitat III new urban agenda declaration

Pop-Machina assets	Declaration 41	Declaration 51	Declaration 52	Declaration 154	Declaration 155
Pop-Machina urban development framework		x	x		
Circular Maker Communities	x			x	x
Circular Makerspaces	x	x	x	x	x
Pop-Machina Maker Academy	x			x	x
Social collaboration platform	x			x	x
Pop-Machina Integration Guide	x			x	x

KPI 27: contribution to the urban agenda for the EU: 7 priority themes

Pop-Machina substantially supports the *Urban Agenda for the EU* in most of its priority themes, including air quality, circular economy, jobs and skills in the local economy, climate adaptation, energy transition, sustainable use of land and nature-based solutions, as well as digital transition. These themes will be covered by the project pilots and the applications of the Pop-Machina platform.

The urban agenda’s priority themes for cities are:

1. air quality;
2. circular economy;
3. climate adaptation;
4. digital transition;
5. energy transition;
6. housing;
7. inclusion of migrants and refugees;
8. innovative and responsible public procurement;
9. jobs and skills in the local economy;
10. sustainable use of land and nature-based solutions;
11. urban mobility;
12. urban poverty.

Pop-Machina substantially supports the *Urban Agenda for the EU*²⁹ in most of its priority themes, including air quality, circular economy, jobs and skills in the local economy, climate adaptation, energy transition, sustainable use of land and nature-based solutions, as well as digital transition.

More specifically project’s assets contribution per priority theme (that was identified in the proposal phase) is analysed in the following:

- Air Quality

The European Commission through the Urban Agenda proposes measures to protect human health that focus on a wide range of pollution sources. As air quality is a key determining factor for the quality of life in cities, better regulation, monitoring and knowledge in this area is necessary. The co-created Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework, with the accompanying toolkit, for urban and peri-urban circularity and regenerative capacity, will monitor indicators, including

²⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/urban-agenda>

sustainability and scalability variables that will help in the monitoring pollution sources that are identified to affect air quality.

- Circular economy

Circular Economy measures within the Urban Agenda cover the whole cycle: from production and consumption to waste management and the market for secondary raw materials. POP-MACHINA is highly relevant to this priority, as it addresses the issue of circular economy throughout the entire production lifecycle, promotes the remodeling of materials of high priority, and activates groundbreaking measures (such as tokenisation) to increase innovation and sustainability of the resulting circular processes.

- Climate Adaptation

Adaptation strategies are needed at local, regional, national, EU and international levels in order to anticipate the adverse effects of climate change and prevent or minimise the damage. Pop-Machina adopts such an adaptation strategy in the urban environment through a novel urban development framework, driven by circularity which also addresses climate adaptation issues. The project's Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework also helps in the monitoring of urban sources that effect climate adaptations.

- Digital Transition

Within the Urban Agenda for the EU on the digital transition, cities, EU countries and the European Commission work together to provide more efficient public services and a better knowledge exchange. Focus is amongst others in eGovernment, 5G, urban planning, future learning and skills development.

To this end Pop-Machina assets contribute with the Maker Academy and social collaboration platform that builds upon FoF technologies promoting learning and skills development. Additionally, the Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework toolkit, for urban and peri-urban circularity and regenerative capacity, the Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism and the tokenisation and incentivisation schemes offer innovative digital support services to the maker ecosystem supported by the project municipalities.

- Energy Transition

The Urban Agenda for the EU on energy transition goal is to have a long-term structural change in energy systems. To this end reductions of greenhouse gas emissions and energy savings are targeted. The Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework toolkit is a project asset that contributes to this theme area by examining technical indicators, amongst which energy indicators, to support evidence of reduced emissions and energy savings and lead to the best energy wise proposed solutions for the maker community.

- Jobs and skills in the local economy

The Job and Skills Agenda for Europe supports a number of actions to ensure that the right training, the right skills and the right support are available to people in the European Union. The Pop-Machina Accelerator with its business development and circular innovation support services will fuel circular entrepreneurship. In addition, Maker Academy and social collaboration platform build upon learning and skills development.

- Sustainable use of land and nature-based solutions

The sustainable city model implies efficient land use and discouragement of urban sprawl. It focuses on 'inward' development, which suggests restoring degraded land, using, recycling and retrofitting land. Such approach entails natural physical, social and economic regeneration. The Pop-Machina novel urban development framework, Circular Maker Communities, and the regenerated Circular Makerspaces to be developed within the pilot cities are all assets directly supporting this priority driven by the local circular collaborative economy.

Inclusion of migrants and refugees, urban poverty and innovative and responsible public procurement are three additional priority themes that are also tackled by Pop-Machina. Migrants and refugees are a vulnerable social group that may be included in the Pop-Machina Circular Maker

Communities that will be set-up during the project, but this depends on the focus group of each pilot. Urban poverty is also tackled by circular Maker Communities with the objective to contribute to the local circular collaborative economy, whilst the integrated social collaboration platform will assist in the sense of offering the community the provisions (cooperation, knowledge sharing) active inclusion and activation of the poor. The use of the tokenisation system is another incentive that could tackle poverty issues as activities and products replace monetary value within the Pop-Machina ecosystem.

Innovative and responsible public procurement is strongly supported by the tokenisation and incentivisation schemes that will be adopted by the project municipalities as well as the Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) mechanism for smart contracts and circularity certification are innovative technological methods used for the promotion of green – circular methods within the project ecosystem.

Table 28. Pop-Machina assets per urban agenda priority theme

Pop-Machina assets	Priority 1	Priority 2	Priority 3	Priority 4	Priority 5	Priority 7	Priority 8	Priority 9	Priority 10	Priority 12
Pop-Machina urban development framework		x	x						x	
Circular Maker Communities		x				x			x	x
Circular Makerspaces		x							x	
Pop-Machina Maker Academy		x		x				x		
Social collaboration platform		x		x				x		x
Online inventory		x								
Circular product/service prototypes		x								
Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework	x	x	x	x	x					
BaaS mechanism		x		x			x			
Tokenisation and Incentivisation Scheme		x		x			x			
Pop-Machina Accelerator		x						x		
Pop-Machina Integration Guide		x								

All the above KPIs are nonetheless dependent on the results of previous WPs and mainly the pilot implementation, as to which extend, they will incorporate these priority themes. The extent of implementation of the policies these KPIs support will be reviewed as the project progresses in the forthcoming deliverables and evidence is presented by pilot implementation.

8. Conclusions

Pop-Machina will have a significant impact in innovative circular economy and collaborative production and relative technological applications, both from a technical and a business perspective. To this end, an innovation and exploitation management plan and strategy has been defined from the early beginning of the project.

This deliverable will also serve as guidance for consortium members and will be updated throughout the development of the project, in order to adjust to the innovation activity requirements. The Innovation, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan is considered as an adaptive living document and it will be further updated according to different project phases. An updated version of the Exploitation plan will be delivered in M24, based on the experience gathered during the first 24 months of the project.

9. References

Weber S. & Scherer J., (6 May 2020) Effective IP and Outreach Strategies Help Increase the Impact of Research and Innovation, <http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/>

Scherer, J., Weber, S., Azofra, M., Ruede A, Sweeney E, Weiler N., Sagias I.,Haardt J., Cravetto R., Spichtinger D., Ala-Mutka K.,(March, 2018) Making the Most of Your H2020 Project Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation? <http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/>

Pitkethly, R. (2007). ip Handbook of best practices CHAPTER NO. 5.1 IP Strategy
<http://www.iphandbook.org/handbook/ch05/p01/>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intellectual_property
<https://www.wipo.int/>

European Commission, Corrigendum to Directive 2004/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004L0048R%2801%29>

European IPR Helpdesk, Fact Sheet IP management in Horizon 2020: at the proposal stage, (February 2014), <http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/>

Kylliäinen, J. (Dec 2018) Innovation Strategy – What is it and how to develop one?
<https://www.viima.com/blog/innovation-strategy>

5G MOBIX, (April 2019) Innovation Management Plan <https://www.5g-mobix.com/assets/files/5G-MOBIX-D1.3-Innovation-Management-Plan-V1.0.pdf>

The Helen MacArthur Foundation, (July 2015) Growth within: a circular economy vision for a competitive Europe, https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/assets/downloads/publications/EllenMacArthurFoundation_Growth-Within_July15.pdf

European Commission, (Jan 2016), Briefing on 'Circular economy package, four legislative proposals on waste', <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/EPRS/EPRS-Briefing-573936-Circular-economy-package-FINAL.pdf>
<https://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/index.htm>
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Waste_statistics

McKinsey & Company, (September, 2015), Europe's circular-economy opportunity
<https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/sustainability/our-insights/europes-circular-economy-opportunity>

European Commission (March, 2020), Changing how we produce and consume: New Circular Economy Action Plan shows the way to a climate-neutral, competitive economy of empowered consumers,
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_420

Rosa, P., Ferretti, F., Guimarães Pereira, Â., Panella, F., & Wanner, M. (2017). Overview of the maker movement in the European Union. Publications Office of the European Union,
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distributed_manufacturing

Mattab D., Raucha E., Dallasegaa P., (2015) Trends towards Distributed Manufacturing Systems and modern forms for their design.

Colchester J., (June 2019), Distributed Manufacturing, <https://systemsinnovation.io/distributed-manufacturing-how-it-works/>

WEF World Economic Forum, (2015), Collaborative Innovation Transforming Business, Driving Growth, http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Collaborative_Innovation_report_2015.pdf

European Commission, (March 2020), Changing how we produce and consume: New Circular Economy Action Plan shows the way to a climate-neutral, competitive economy of empowered consumers,
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_420

Metzger E., Puft del Pino S., Prowitt S., Goodward J., Perera A., WORLD RESOURCES INSTITUTE, 2012 sSWOT A sustainability SWOT, http://pdf.wri.org/sustainability_swot_user_guide.pdf

European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Closing the loop - An EU action

plan for the Circular Economy COM/2015/0614 final <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52015DC0614>

UN, The New Urban Agenda, <http://habitat3.org/the-new-urban-agenda/>

European Commission, Urban Agenda for the EU, <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/urban-agenda>

Berariu R., Munteanu M, Condurache G., Butnaru R., (January 2011) Analysis of Sustainable Development Strategies Using SWOT Conference Paper, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/216089280_ANALYSIS_OF_SUSTAINABLE_DEVELOPMENT_STRATEGY_USING_SWOT

About Pop-Machina

Pop-Machina aims to demonstrate the power and potential of the maker movement and collaborative production for the EU circular economy. We draw from a number of cut-edge technologies (factory-of-the-future, blockchain) and disciplines (urban planning, architecture) to provide the support necessary to overcome scaling issues; a typical drawback of collaborative production; to find the areas more in need of our intervention and to reconfigure unused spaces. We put forth an elaborate community engagement programme to network, incentivise and stimulate through maker faires and events existing and new maker communities in all our municipalities. We build upon the current informal curriculum for maker skills development by nurturing the social side and we put educators and makers together to exchange ideas on the training modalities. A particular focus on the skill development of women and vulnerable groups will aim to empower these (underrepresented) segments to partake actively in collaborative production. In every pilot area we will demonstrate business oriented collaborative production of feasible and sustainable concepts from secondary raw material or other sustainable inputs, based on the needs and preferences of the local stakeholders. A thorough impact assessment framework with increased scope (e.g. social) will be co-designed with stakeholders after short basic assessment trainings and will be used in the assessment of our pilot work. Based on the findings we will kick-start a series of policy events to discuss openly – without pushing our results – the tax and legal barriers that hamper collaborative production.

Coordinator

HIVA - Research Institute for Work and Society
Behavioral Engineering Research Group
KU Leuven (BE)

Partners

City of Leuven (BE)
ETAM (GR)
Municipality of Thessaloniki (GR)
Municipality of Piraeus (GR)
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL (GR)
University of Macedonia (GR)
Ayuntamiento de Santander (ES)
Universidad de Cantabria (ES)
Gemeente Venlo, KanDoen (NL)
TU Delft (NL)
Istanbul Metropolitan University (TR)
İSTAÇ AŞ (TR)
Planet Turkey (TR)
Koç University (TR)
Municipality of Kaunas (LT)
ISM University of Management and Economics (LT)
University of Cambridge (UK)
CERTH (GR)
White Research (BE)
CommonLawgic (GR)
INTRASOFT International (LU)
Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (ES)

VISIT: <http://www.pop-machina.eu>

CONTACT US: pop-machina@kuleuven.be

FOLLOW US:

